

The Importance of Social Sciences in Arming the Student Youth Consciousness with Noble Virtues

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ABSTRACT: The article examines the issues of understanding national identity, the formation of national unity, greatness and purity of our ancestry, assessing the place of our wise people among the peoples of the world, wider use of its rich life experience, the importance of the social sciences in the consistent study and further enrichment of the noble, freedom-loving and liberal traditions of our people, in short, in the creation of a harmonious, real human personality.

KEYWORDS: Intellectual ability, independence, worldview, national cadre, education system, harmoniously developed generation, reform, national independence, noble character, social sciences, religious tolerance, ideological immunity.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that the power of this or that state, the level of development depends on the intellectual abilities, knowledge and skills of the citizens of this state. Only a country with a mature and well-developed staff that meets the requirements of the times will face development. Therefore, from the first days of independence, special attention was paid to the training of highly qualified and innovative national cadres, radical reform of the education system, among the most important issues in our lives, Raising it to the level of modern requirements, upbringing and bringing up a harmoniously developed generation has been in the focus of the state leadership, because, as the first President Islam Karimov said, "in the event of reforms in all spheres of life in our country, It is important to change the worldview of the people, to train personnel that meet the requirements of the times in the realization of our noble dream of building a great state". In our country, the upbringing of a mature and harmoniously developed person has always been an urgent task. In this sense, today in the framework of practical work, special attention is paid to educating the younger generation in the spirit of firm beliefs and views on life and bringing them up on the basis of national and universal values that can withstand harmful social evils alien to our mentality. "All these works, all our reforms are aimed at a great and unique goal. It is to preserve the peace and tranquility of our people, to increase the welfare of the population, to bring up our children as healthy and harmonious people"[13].

The power of any country depends on its independence, the inviolability of its borders, the fact that the citizens of that country are brought up with love for their country, and have such noble qualities as readiness to sacrifice their lives in the struggle for national independence. The role and opportunities of the social sciences in the decision-making and formation of these qualities in our people, and most importantly, the future of our country - the minds of young people are endless.

As a result of the policy pursued by the Communist Party during the years of Soviet rule, the issue of teaching the history of our country in schools, secondary special and higher education institutions of Uzbekistan has not received much attention. In those years, the real history of our country was not created objectively. Textbooks and literature taught in schools and educational institutions have falsified our history. As a result, the spiritual life of the Uzbek people has deteriorated, the political consciousness of the people has faded, the feeling of indifference and indifference to socio-political events has increased. Because it was possible to establish domination over the enslaved peoples by keeping them in political darkness and obscurity.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

A. Augustine said, "To awaken a nation lying in ignorance, first awaken its history"[14.8]. Today, a true, literal history of our native people has been created. We have had the opportunity to study history objectively - as it is in practice. History helps to determine the direction of programmatic actions based on the analysis of all events and happenings, thinking and drawing vital conclusions from them.

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In understanding the national identity, in the formation of national unity, in knowing the greatness and purity of our family tree, in assessing the place of our wise people among the peoples of the world, in the wider use of its rich life experiences, The role of the social sciences in the consistent study and further enrichment of the noble, freedom-loving and liberal traditions of our people, in short, in the creation of a harmonious, true human personality, is enormous.

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Islam Karimov, said “We are creating conditions for all our people, including our youth, to enjoy the sacred heritage of our thinkers, to grow up in a spiritual environment, and for the humane philosophy and great ideas of Islam to take root in the hearts of the younger generation”. In other words, we are educating our children on the basis of the Hadiths, the teachings of Naqshbandi, the teachings of Tirmidhi, the Wisdoms of Yassavi, collected by Imam Bukhari, as well as secular knowledge”, he said.

World-famous and well-known thinkers have written their views on the education of young people in their works.

In the philosophical and pedagogical views of the ancient Greek philosopher Socrates, the expected goal of upbringing is to achieve the acquisition of knowledge by man, to perfect him as a high moral being. In his teaching, he defines the concepts of courage, wisdom, moderation, justice. According to him, courage is to repel fear, wisdom is to follow the laws of society, moderation is not to give free rein to one’s feelings.

According to the teachings of Socrates, man must first and foremost possess the general moral standards, the qualities that are sacred to man.

The famous Greek philosopher Platon expressed his views on the organization of education in his works “The State and the Laws”. In his view, the influence of adults on children is reflected in the content of moral qualities in children. He believes that affecting emotions is the basis of raising young children.

According to the teachings of the ancient Greek thinker Aristotle, upbringing should be carried out taking into account the age characteristics of children. Aristotle defined the period of upbringing as 21 years - from birth to 7 years, from 7 to 14 years, from 14 to 21 years. It shows the specificity of each period of the child, describes the purpose, content and methods of education carried out in each period.

Farabi emphasizes the need to pay special attention to mental and moral education in educating young people to be perfect human beings, in his opinion, knowledge, enlightenment must be adorned with good morals, otherwise the expected goal will not be achieved, the child will not mature.

Ibn Sina says in his views on the moral upbringing of the child that the most important means is to have a one-on-one conversation, to admonish him, without touching the child's instincts and pride. Ibn Sina considers the formation of moral qualities in the child in unity with labor, physical and mental upbringing, as a key factor in his development as a human being.

According to Yusuf Khas Hajib, everyone should be worthy of society and develop. To do this, he must receive the necessary upbringing from the day of birth.

Mirzo Ulugbek’s views on raising a healthy generation in a family environment are based on the fact that, according to the scientist, the environment in which a child is brought up plays an important role in increasing his interest in education. In the family, parents, especially educated parents, should pay special attention to the development of their children into real human beings. He paid great attention to the intellectual and enlightenment upbringing of the younger generation and encouraged them to acquire worldly knowledge. Only advanced science and culture believe that human thinking can be perfected.

Alisher Navoi pays special attention to the power and strength of upbringing in the development of a child. He believes that as a result of upbringing, the child will grow into a useful and mature person.

In his pedagogical views, the preacher Al-Kashifi pays special attention to the development of children’s ability to think independently. The child should be brought up to be truthful, faithful to promises, and well-behaved.

Jaloliddin Davoni Parents’ equal, equal participation of the child, the rules of good behavior of the child, assistance in the acquisition of a certain profession should be attractive to.

According to Muslihiddin Sadi Sherozi, one of the great representatives of Eastern classical literature, a child can be gifted and incompetent. Ability does not develop spontaneously. For its development it is necessary to bring up the child, without upbringing the ability in the child will disappear. There are 3 main types of education - mental, sophisticated and physical.

In his works, Kamil Khorezimi promoted the ideas of enlightenment, moral maturity and patriotism. He also expresses his pedagogical views on the welfare of the people, society, the role of man in the development of morality, the integral unity of moral and ethical education.

The effective use of the heritage of Central Asian thinkers in the formation of an objective worldview of religion among young people is also effective. Consequently, their unique spiritual heritage will lead to a further increase in their interest in the fields of science by educating our youth.

Therefore, we need to intensify educational work to promote the scientific, spiritual, religious and enlightenment heritage of our great ancestors, to preserve the material and spiritual property created today.

The Eastern thinker Abu Nasr al-Farabi, in his teaching, dwelled on education and upbringing, describing the circumstances of these two processes, and arguing that where they come together, man’s interest in the profession arises: “Education is about

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words and learning. Education, on the other hand, is the study of practical work and experience, that is, the fact that this people, this nation, is committed to the profession of labor, which consists of practical skills. If they are devoted to work, to the profession, if they are interested in the profession, if this interest attracts them to the profession, then they will be a true lover of the profession”.

The social sciences are able to take an active part in the social life of our independent state, to understand their historical roots, to develop a generation full of boundless love for their country, motherland and people, to instill in their minds the ideas of national independence and military patriotism. In this regard, the First President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov has paid great attention to the study of the history of Uzbekistan, teaching it to young people, from kindergartens to universities. Islam Karimov – “The path traversed by a nation with a fully restored sense of historical memory will be true history only if it is studied objectively and truthfully with all its successes and victories, losses and victims, joys and sorrows”[15.97], – his views are of immense importance.

As a logical continuation of this noble work, great reforms have been carried out in our country in a short period of time. The head of our state Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to the appreciation of the spiritual heritage of our people and the development of enlightened Islam.

It is important for both teachers and students to master the subjects, to supplement, repeat, reinforce the knowledge given in the course, to correctly introduce rating control. Teachers and educators need to ensure the effective use of students' time budget, to avoid unrealistic, biased, superficial, formal, liberal in the assessment of their knowledge, to teach students consistently, they are required to perform their duties responsibly, such as imparting thorough knowledge, and to work on themselves on a regular basis. Students should master the knowledge set out in the curriculum.

Physical, mental, physiological, spiritual and moral processes also play an important role in the acquisition of noble qualities by young people. It is no coincidence that all judges and doctors have always paid attention to physical education. Because physical health provides mental, intellectual, and moral health. So the acceptance of upbringing also depends on physical upbringing. Physical training is physical training. When the body is physically strong, it brings out the qualities of courage and perseverance in a person. There are certain goals in physical education. That is, maintaining and strengthening good health, strengthening the human organs, ensuring physical strength. In the family, in kindergarten, at school, paying attention to the height of children, its correct formation also affects the upbringing. Strengthening the bone joints, muscles, cardiovascular system, respiratory organs, all nerve fibers in the body is a guarantee of human health. To do this, each person must be in constant motion. According to the scholar Abu Ali ibn Sina, physical training is a glorious way of maintaining good health. Yes, whoever is on the move will always be blessed by it. Movement is also an exercise. In order to acquire knowledge, one also reads more, because exercise ensures the health of the body.

It has been found that many students achieve low scores in completing test assignments in the social sciences for admission to higher education after vocational college or academic lyceum education. It is very difficult for young people to read, study, work on a book, think logically about problematic issues, analyze, summarize the details of events, evaluate them, express their attitude to this or that historical event, draw appropriate conclusions, connect with everyday life and time. This situation is also strongly influenced by the lack of control and demands on students, the damage caused to the educational process due to the fact that various public events are held at the expense of lessons and other activities.

It is necessary to bring the knowledge of young people to the required level of knowledge, to raise the level of knowledge, to inculcate in them the knowledge of these subjects within the framework of the State Educational Standard, to achieve the formation of thorough knowledge in science. They need to be taught the latest history of our country on the eve of independence. They need to feel from the bottom of their hearts that our people did not achieve independence easily.

Today, modern, new forms of information and pedagogical technologies have been introduced to help young people to take a firm stand against attacks under the guise of “mass culture”, religious extremism, international terrorism, the “export” of ideas and values alien to our people. Naturally, in this regard, it is important to widely promote and propagate the high masterpieces of real works of art against the low-level, light-hearted examples of “popular culture”.

The issue of raising a spiritually and physically harmoniously developed generation is a national task for us.

It is well known that one of the individuals who form an integral part of life, formed as a doctrine of life, is man. Man cannot live in isolation from biological processes as well as outside society. “Man was created for society. He is not fit to live alone and does not dare to live alone” (U. Blackstone).

One of the important characteristics of man is that he is a social being. One of the important characteristics of a person is that he is a social being. In sociology, there is a concept of ‘socialization of the individual. As the individual is formed under the influence of the social environment, the concept of ‘socialization’ is used to describe this process. The socialization of an individual is the process by which a social being (human being) assimilates social norms and cultural values throughout his or her life in the family, kindergarten, educational institutions, community, and finally in society. The concept of “socialization” is related to the concepts of “nurturing the individual”, “shaping the individual”, but it is broader and encompasses all the influences directed at the person.

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The socialization of man acquires an artificial character, and he as a person can be formed only among other people. If he is free from human relations, he cannot get rid of his evil or animal nature. Abu Nasr al-Farabi describes this natural feature in man as follows: "Everyone is structured by his nature in such a way that he needs a lot of things to live and achieve a high level of maturity, he cannot achieve such things alone, there is a need for a community of people to have them ... Therefore, it is only through the necessities of life, the supply of people to one another, and mutual assistance, that man can attain the maturity he aspires to by nature. The activities of such team members as a whole provide each of them with the things they need to live and mature. Therefore, human beings multiplied and settled in the inhabited part of the earth, and as a result, a human community was formed"[16.186].

The modern task of every educator is to raise the spiritual maturity of young people, to form in them religious tolerance, political-legal, environmental knowledge and culture, ideological immunity and ideological struggle, to create a healthy spiritual and socio-psychological worldview, a healthy lifestyle, to propagate and inculcate in them physical culture, morals. To train them to meet the highest spiritual and moral requirements, to understand the domestic and foreign policies of the state, to be patriotic and nationalistic, enterprising and entrepreneurial, armed with modern knowledge and high human qualities, strong-willed, faithful and conscientious. It is to protect students from the vices of human trafficking, various other destructive threats and religious extremist influences alien to us, from attacks of inferior "mass culture", to prevent any actions aimed at promoting violence, shamelessness and cruelty in society.

The reforms being carried out in our country, the achievements in various fields, the work being done to educate the younger generation, which is an important part of society, the solution of some problems, along with the creative work, is to increase awareness and vigilance.

- ❖ It is advisable to further develop activities in the following areas:
 - ✓ to protect our youth from the threat of biased information that harms their spiritual and moral development;
 - ✓ Further promotion of educational issues in the works of Central Asian thinkers, extensive use of their educational teachings;
 - ✓ to highlight the great goals of the works of thinkers in the life of society, the great creativity behind it, the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation, to disseminate the developments aimed at promoting their works to the general public;
 - ✓ formation of skills and potential in each young generation living in our country to understand the changes taking place in the environment and to express their views on them;
 - ✓ raising the socio-political and ideological worldview among students, forming a sense of respect for our spirituality, national values and traditions, the hearts and minds of young people, to pay special attention to spiritual and educational work, which requires the struggle for common sense, to focus on new methods and mechanisms of inculcating spirituality in the minds of young people;
 - ✓ Thirty years - to widely disseminate among our youth the results of development and progress achieved during the years of independence in the political sphere, state and society building, economy and spirituality, social life, judiciary, foreign policy and security; to inculcate in the hearts and minds of the younger generation the incomparable importance of independence, that it is a source of great opportunities, to instill in them a sense of love and devotion to the Motherland;
 - ✓ The greatest wealth we have achieved during the years of independence is the noble qualities of our people, such as the peaceful and serene life, mutual respect, kindness and tolerance in society, achieving an understanding that the principle of living in accordance with national and universal values is becoming stronger is an important part of the future plan of educational work.

There are a number of problems in education. It is very difficult for young people to read, study, work on a book, think logically, analyze problematic issues, summarize the details of events, evaluate them, express their attitude to a particular historical event, draw appropriate conclusions, connect with everyday life and time. This situation is also strongly influenced by the lack of control and demands on students, the damage caused to the educational process due to the fact that various public events are held at the expense of lessons and other activities.

Strict control should be exercised over the observance of ethical principles, rules of conduct and obligations by the student in relation to the educational institution. Adherence to them will help to create a healthy spiritual and socio-psychological environment in the school, to preserve its prestige and prestige, to help prepare a harmoniously developed generation that meets the highest spiritual and moral requirements, serves to further enhance the prestige of the school in society and in the education system. The main tasks of educational institutions are to have high moral and ethical qualities, to feel their responsibility to society, the state and the family, to bring up young people with a strong will, strong faith and a clear conscience, who have a correct understanding of the domestic and foreign policy of the state, who are patriotic and nationalistic, enterprising and enterprising, armed with modern knowledge and high human qualities, to form, maintain and protect their spiritual immunity, including the prevention of any conduct aimed at violating morals among young people, including the promotion of violence, immorality and cruelty; it should never be forgotten that it consists in helping to protect young people from the evils of alcoholism and drug abuse, various other destructive threats, and from religious extremist influences that are alien to us.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the political teachings of Islam Karimov and Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Uzbekistan has built a democratic state governed by the rule of law, fulfilling the centuries-old aspirations of our people, and forming a civil society. Our efforts to bring up our children on the basis of high spiritual values, to equip their minds with high human qualities will take their place among the great work being done in our country for the welfare of our people.

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